

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-53-IA-10% rac	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	21	Acq. Method Set:	10%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	LRM 4 53
Injection Volume:	1.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/29/2022 14:56:19 CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 19:57:06 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.923	2737162	50.29	313489
2	8.166	2705166	49.71	262889

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-59-IA-10% asy	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	21	Acq. Method Set:	10%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	LRM 4 59
Injection Volume:	3.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	15.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/29/2022 15:56:29 CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 19:56:04 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.935	930033	5.12	109312
2	8.163	17236191	94.88	1648222